

BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS AND CYTOTOXICITY ASSESSMENT OF DIPLAZIUM ESCULENTUM LEAF EXTRACTS

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ABSTRACT

Diplazium esculentum, an edible fern widely consumed and used in traditional medicine across Asia, was investigated for its phytochemical composition and biological activity. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) analysis of leaf extracts revealed the presence of essential oils, flavonoids, steroids, tannins, alkaloids, and phenols. The cytotoxicity of the extract was evaluated using the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BSLA) and *Allium Cepa* Test. The BSLA results showed that the extract was non-toxic to *Artemia salina* nauplii at different concentrations, with LC50 values of 18,706 ppm at 24 h and 112,490 ppm at 48 h, indicating low toxicity. The *Allium Cepa* Test revealed no chromosomal aberrations and a high mitotic index of 66.66, further confirming the low cytotoxicity of the extract. The antibacterial activity of the crude extract was assessed using disc diffusion or Kirby-Bauer assays against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The zones of inhibition of the extract-impregnated discs were compared to those of the positive controls, Meropenem for *E. coli* and Clindamycin for *S. aureus*. The results showed that both bacterial strains were resistant to the extract, with average zones of inhibition of 9.74 mm for *E. coli* and 10.49 mm for *S. aureus*, indicating low antimicrobial activity. Despite the presence of various secondary metabolites, the *D. esculentum* leaf extracts exhibited low cytotoxicity and antimicrobial activity, suggesting that they may not be suitable for antibiotic development. Future studies should explore alternative plant parts, extraction techniques, and biological activities to elucidate the therapeutic potential of this edible fern.

Keywords: *Antimicrobial Activity, Bioactive Compounds, Biological Activities, Cytotoxicity, Phytochemical Composition, Traditional Medicine*

INTRODUCTION

Diplazium esculentum, commonly known in the Philippines as "paco," is an edible fern that is widely distributed throughout Asia, Africa, Oceania, and North America (Roy et al., 2013). This herbaceous fern is particularly prevalent in Malaysia and other regions worldwide, where it is consumed as both food and medicine. The significance of ferns in traditional medicine has been well-documented across different cultures. In Central Kalimantan, Dayak people use *D. esculentum* to treat tumors, asthma, and acne (Zannah et al., 2017). Its ethnomedicinal importance extends to the treatment of various health disorders in different plant parts (rhizomes, shoots, fronds, and leaves) (Raina et al., 2023). Recent studies emphasize the dual role of plants in environmental and therapeutic applications. For example, *Ipomoea reptans* Poir (Kangkong) has been studied for its phytoremediation potential in lead-contaminated hydroponic systems, where it effectively accumulates lead from polluted environments, indicating its usefulness in environmental cleanup (Ingente & Anselmo, 2024). This ecological role highlights the bioactive capabilities of plant species, including *Diplazium esculentum*, whose leaf extracts contain various secondary metabolites such as essential oils, flavonoids, and tannins. Despite exhibiting low cytotoxicity and antimicrobial activity, *D. esculentum* contributes valuable data to the understanding of plant bioactivity, paralleling the research on *Ipomoea reptans*, which expands our view of plants beyond their environmental roles to their potential in health applications.

Diplazium esculentum grows in marshy areas, streambanks, and canals. It is characterized by an erect rhizome, scaly apex, and can grow 1 m tall. The taxonomic classification is as follows: Kingdom, Plantae; Division, Pteridophyta; Class-Polypodiopsida; Order-Polypodiales; Family-Athyriaceae; Genus-Diplazium; and Species- *D. esculentum* (Roy & Chaudhuri, 2020). The growing global interest in plant-based research to identify bioactive compounds with therapeutic potential is closely linked to the worldwide trend of seeking natural remedies. This shift is driven by concerns over synthetic additives in processed foods and the desire for more natural plant-based functional foods (Chua & Nicholas, 2023). Interestingly, the popularity of plant-based remedies has increased worldwide over the last 30 years, partly because natural-product-based diets and herbal-based preparations are safe and have been used for centuries. This revival of interest in traditional foods and medicinal plants has led to intensive research on their safety, efficacy, and mechanisms of action at the cellular, biochemical, and molecular levels (Riaz et al., 2016).

Plant-based secondary metabolites have attracted significant attention because of their diverse biological activities and potential applications in various fields. These compounds, produced by plants and their associated microorganisms, exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties including antimicrobial, cytotoxic, anti-inflammatory, and antiviral activities (Agrawal et al., 2023; Ancheeva et al., 2020). Endophytes are microorganisms that colonize internal plant tissues and have been identified as a rich source of bioactive secondary metabolites. These compounds not only enhance the fitness of host plants, but also possess medicinal properties, making them valuable for drug discovery (Ancheeva et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2018). Similarly, fungi, particularly

those associated with forest trees, produce a goldmine of secondary metabolites with diverse biological activities including phytotoxic, antifungal, antibacterial, and cytotoxic properties (Masi et al., 2018). Interestingly, some endophytes can biosynthesize "phytochemicals," which were originally believed to be produced only by their host plants, offering potential alternative sources for these valuable compounds (Ancheeva et al., 2020). This discovery opens new avenues for the sustainable production of bioactive plant metabolites.

Diplazium esculentum is important in various traditional medicinal practices and is a nutritious food source, making it a valuable subject for plant-based research. It is widely used in traditional medicine to address a diverse range of health issues such as diabetes, smallpox, rheumatism, and hypertension (Semwal et al., 2021), and its wide array of reported activities, including anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antifungal, and antioxidant properties, suggest promising applications in nutraceutical or functional food formulations (Raina et al., 2023).

However, various studies have argued that there are limitations to its phytochemical composition, cytotoxicity, and biological activities. Semwal et al. (2021) claimed that despite the presence of ethnomedicinal, phytochemical, and pharmacological properties, few researchers have validated its nutraceutical and pharmacological properties, leading to the scientific and medical community's belief that there is not enough evidence to develop medicine out of it. Kumar & Parasurama (2024) suggested the need for systematic investigations of plant's profile, including potential bioactive compounds, such as phenolics, flavonoids, terpenoids, and alkaloids, their cytotoxicity against different cell lines (Cannas et al., 2015), and antibacterial properties against various pathogens (Jaradat et al., 2024). Hence, this study aims to contribute to the study of the phytochemical and biological properties of the leaves of *D. esculentum*.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the phytochemical components and biological activities of *Diplazium esculentum*. Specifically, it aimed to

1. Determine the secondary metabolites present in the leaf extracts through Thin Layer Chromatography,
2. The cytotoxicity of the extract was determined using the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BSLA) and the *Allium Cepa* Test.
3. Determination of Antibacterial Activity of the crude extract.

METHODOLOGY

Collection and Extraction of *Diplazium Esculentum*

Mature fern leaves were collected along the rivers of Ablang, Brgy. Communal, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The leaves were washed, chopped, and air-dried for two weeks. Free-

from-moist leaves were pulverized in a blender. To produce a crude extract, pulverized leaves were soaked in ethanol for 48 h in a percolator and evaporated in a water bath at 50°C.

Thin Layer Chromatography

The crude extract of fern spotted on the TLC paper was developed using ethyl acetate and chloroform, which gave the best separation of the compounds. They were then visualized and marked using different reagents, such as Vanillin Sulfuric Acid, alpha-naphthol sulfuric acid, potassium ferricyanide-ferric chloride, Methanolic KOH, Dragendorff, Antimony (III) Chloride, and Magnesium Acetate, to determine the class of compounds present.

Cytotoxic Assay

The cytotoxicity of the extract was determined by Brine Shrimp Lethality assay (BSLA) and Allium Cepa Test.

Sample Preparation for BSLA

The microplate was then filled with 1 ml of artificial salt water. Approximately 37 mg of crude extract was weighed, placed in a test tube, and dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide and 17 ml of saltwater to obtain a 2000 ppm solution. One milliliter of solution was transferred from the test tube to the first column of the microplate. Two-fold serial dilutions were performed to obtain concentrations (ppm) of 2000, 1000, 500, 250, 125, and 62.5.

Hatching the Shrimp

Brine Shrimp (*A. salina*) eggs were hatched in a compartment petri dish filled with artificial salt water (SMU-CNS standard measurement: 19 g sea salt pure NaCl, dissolved in 500 ml of distilled water), kept under constant aeration and illumination. After 48 h of incubation, the nauplii were collected using a pipette.

Bioassay

The microplate contained 2000 ppm, 1000 ppm, 500, 250, 125, and 62.5 ppm concentrations. A minimum of 10 brine shrimp nauplii were loaded at each concentration using a pipette. Four replicates were used for each concentration. The setup was placed in a standard room temperature environment. Live shrimps were counted after 24 and 48 h. using a digital microscope. The Percent mortality was computed, and the LC50 was determined using Probit Analysis. The formula below was used to calculate the mortality rate.

$$\% \text{ Death} = \frac{\text{Number of dead nauplii}}{\text{Number of dead nauplii} + \text{Number of live nauplii}} \times 100$$

Allium Cepa Test

The solution was prepared by weighing 2 mg of the crude extract diluted in 1 liter of distilled water. Two-fold serial dilutions were performed to obtain concentrations of 2000, 1000, 500, 250, and 125 ppm. Cultivated onions were treated with different

concentrations for 48 h. After treatment, a 2 cm root tip was collected at 12–1 midnight and arrested in Carnoy's fluid.

Root tips were placed in a petri dish with 1 N HCl for 10 min, dipped in distilled water, and transferred to a petri dish with acetocarmine for 5-10 minutes for staining. The stained root tips were transferred to a glass slide, covered, and gently squashed using the eraser of a Mongol 2 pencil. After squashing, fresh slides were observed under LPO and HPO using a compound microscope. The parameters used to determine toxicity were mitotic index and observation of chromosomal aberration. The formula for calculating the mitotic index is as follows:

$$MI = \frac{\text{\# of dividing cells in all phases}}{\text{\# of dividing cells + non-dividing cells}} \times 100$$

Determination of the Antibacterial Properties

Disc diffusion or Kirby- Bauer assays were employed to examine the antibiotic properties of *Diplazium esculentum*. Nutrient media and bacterial broth were obtained from the SMU Center for Natural Sciences. To prepare the culture plate, the bacterial broth was evenly spread on agar using a sterile swab following proper sterilization. Paper discs were submerged in the crude extract for 24 h. The paper disc impregnated with the extract was transferred to culture plates using forceps. Next, the discs of the positive and negative controls were examined.

The Positive controls used for the four replicates of *E. Coli* bacteria were ten ug Meropenem (MeM) and clindamycin for the three replicates of *S. Aureus* bacteria. A disc soaked in ethanol was used as the negative control. After placing the discs, the samples were wrapped with paper and incubated at 35°C for 24 h. After incubation, the inhibition zone of the discs was measured using a digital caliper. The diameter of the ZOI made by the paper disc and the positive and negative controls was recorded. The collected data were analyzed using the Zone Diameter Interpretative Standards table. The analysis determines whether the disc, with respect to the positive control, is Resistant, Intermediate, or Susceptible.

RESULTS AND DISCUSION

Thin Layer Chromatographic Screening of the Secondary Metabolites

Phytochemical Screening showed that in *Diplazium esculentum* (Edible Fern), the present compounds included essential oils, flavonoids, steroids, tannins, alkaloids, and phenols.

Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay and Allium Cepa Test (Cytotoxicity Bioassays)

Because of the presence of secondary metabolites in the extract, it is worthwhile to determine the toxicity level through Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay and Allium Cepa Test. Sarah et al. (2017) suggested that the Brine Shrimp Lethality assay is an essential tool for the preliminary assessment of the cytotoxicity of plant extract based on the ability to kill a hatched nauplii. At the same time, *Allium cepa* and onion root tips are suitable indicator plants for the determination of potential genotoxic agents in plant extracts due to their relatively large chromosomes, which are appropriate for the detection of chromosomal aberrations (Firbas & Amon, 2014). Table 1 presents the percentage mortality and lethal concentration (LC50) of the extract.

Table 1. Percent Mortality and Lethal Concentration (LC50) of *Diplazium Esculentum* on Brine Shrimp (*A. Salina*) Cytotoxic Assay

Concentrations (ppm)	Total # of Brine shrimp	Average of dead BS after 24 hrs	% of death	Average of dead BS after 48 hrs	% of Death
2000	40	31	78	39	98
1000	40	28	70	40	100
500	40	27	68	37	93
250	40	33	83	37	93
125	40	37	93	40	100
62.5	40	28	70	40	100
LC50= 18706			LC50= 112490		

Figure 1. The Regression line equation of the BSLA Cytotoxicity after 24 hrs

Figure 2. The Regression line equation of the BSLA Cytotoxicity after 48 hrs

The lethal concentration (LC50) is the dosage of *Diplazium esculentum* needed to kill brine shrimp. The LC50 was calculated by substituting 50 for Y in the given Y and R-value of a linear trend line to find the value of X. Based on the data, the LC50 at 24 h was 18, 706, and 112,490 at 48 h. According to a study by Surya et al. (2022). If the LC50 value is ≤ 30 , the toxicity level is very high. If the value is ≤ 31 but ≤ 1000 , the level is toxic. If the LC50 value is >1000 , the level becomes nontoxic (Surya et al., 2022). Hence, the LC50 in this study fell into the non-toxic range.

Mitotic Index on *Allium Cepa* Test

The mitotic index is a measure of the frequency of cell division.

$$\text{MI} = \frac{\text{\# of dividing cells in all phases}}{\text{\# of dividing cells + non-dividing cells}} \times 100$$

$$\text{MI} = \frac{\text{\# of dividing cells in all phases}}{\text{\# of dividing cells + non-dividing cells}} \times 100$$

$$\text{MI} = \frac{90}{90 + 45} \times 100$$

MI = 66.66

The region used in the computation of the mitotic index was that of the root tip exposed to the highest concentration (2000 ppm). The cells marked with white X are in the prophase, the initial mitotic stage.

The above computation shows a high Mitotic Index value. As the Mitotic Index is inversely proportional to cytotoxicity, the toxicity of the crude extract at 2000 ppm was low, suggesting low toxicity in subsequent dilutions.

In addition, the observation of prepared slides of the root tips showed that the majority of the cells were at prophase, and few were at metaphase, anaphase, and late telophase. Nevertheless, the few mitotic stages showed no chromosomal aberrations, indicating that the concentrations were non-toxic.

Antibacterial Properties

The examination of antibiotic properties of *Diplazium esculentum* through disc diffusion or Kirby-Bauer assay shows the following data on the Zone of Inhibition of discs impregnated with crude extract: positive and negative discs. The diameter of the following ZOI was analyzed using a table of Zone Diameter Interpretative Standards. Table 2 shows a summary of the zone of inhibition (diameter) of the three variables in the four replicates of *E. coli*.

	A	B	C	D	AVERAGE
<i>Diplazium Esculentum</i>	8.40 mm	9.31 mm	7.24 mm	14.00 mm	9.7375
Meropenem (MeM) (+)	31.86 mm	31.42 mm	30.91 mm	29.21 mm	30.85
Negative Control	6.88 mm	9.28 mm	8.43 mm	6.71 mm	7.825

It can be gleaned from the table that the diameter of the Zone of Inhibition of *Diplazium esculentum* is 9.74, the Meropenem has 30.85 ZOI, and the Negative control has 7.83 ZOI. Rahman et al. (2021) provided the Zone Diameter Interpretative Standards for *E. coli* bacteria. The table provided was used to interpret the ZOI of the disc of the sample with respect to that of meropenem. As stated, *E. coli* is resistant to a sample disc with a $ZOI \leq 14$, intermediate if it ranges from 16 to 22, and Susceptible if the ZOI is ≥ 21 . Subsequently, the *E. coli* bacteria were resistant to discs impregnated with *Diplazium Esculentum* extract, having a ZOI diameter of 9.735.

Table 3 summarizes the zone of inhibition (diameter) of the three variables in the three replicates of *S. Aureus*.

	A	B	C	AVERAGE
<i>Diplazium Esculentum</i>	9.38 mm	11.72 mm	10.38 mm	10.49333
2 ug Clindamycin (+)	19.61 mm	21.30 mm	21.72 mm	20.87667
Negative Control	13.82 mm	10.68 mm	11.16 mm	11.88667

The table for the zone of inhibition for *S. Aureus* bacteria shows that clindamycin, the positive control, had an average ZOI of 20.88, the highest among the three ZOI. *Diplazium esculentum* had 10.493, while the negative control had 11.89 ZOI. Hudzicki (2009) proposed Zone Diameter Interpretative Standards for *Staphylococcus* species. These were used to compare the ZOI of the disc of the sample with respect to the clindamycin disc. Accordingly, if the Zone of Inhibition was ≤ 14 , the *Staphylococcus* bacteria were resistant to the extract. If the ZOI of the extract ranged from 15 to 20, it fell to the intermediate level.

However, *Staphylococcus* bacteria are susceptible to the extract if the ZOI is ≥ 21 . For the *Diplazium esculentum* disc, the average ZOI was 10.493, indicating resistance to clindamycin.

Diplazium esculentum, which has a low Zone of Inhibition, can be interpreted as having low antimicrobial activity. The Zone Diameter Interpretative Standards for *E. Coli* and *S. Aureus* support this interpretation, showing that the two bacteria used were resistant to the crude extract. Hence, *Diplazium esculentum*, an edible fern, is not suitable for antibiotic development.

This is aligned with the results of the study conducted by Roy and Chaudhuri (2020), who stated that only the rhizome and root of *Diplazium esculentum*, extracted using the aqueous method, inhibited bacterial growth, but the leaf extracts did not show any inhibition.

Conclusions

The results obtained from this study show that essential oils, flavonoids, steroids, tannins, alkaloids, and phenols are present in *Diplazium esculentum*. Because of the presence of secondary metabolites in the extract, the toxicity level was determined using the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay and Allium Cepa Test. The BSLA data shows that at different concentrations, the extract is not toxic to nauplii of *A. Salina*, having LC50 interpreted as non-toxic according to the Toxicity Level of Wagner (1993). In the Allium Cepa Test, the morphological characteristics of chromosomes in the root tips showed no aberration at different mitotic phases. Additionally, the computed mitotic index was high, indicating a low toxicity.

Antibiotic properties are examined through Disc Diffusion or Kirby-Bauer assay. The Zone of inhibition (ZOI) of the disc impregnated with the crude extract was compared to the positive and negative controls used for *E. coli* and *S. Aureus* bacteria. The diameter of the ZOI was compared that with of the Zone Diameter Interpretative Standards. The results showed that *E. coli* and *S. Aureus* were resistant to discs impregnated with the sample, indicating low antimicrobial activity. It can be concluded that *Diplazium esculentum*, despite the presence of secondary metabolites, has low cytotoxicity and low antimicrobial activity. Hence, it is not feasible for antibiotic development

Recommendations

Considering the findings and conclusion, this study suggests that future researchers should consider using the stems, mature leaves, or roots of edible ferns. Future studies should also explore alternative extraction techniques besides percolation to extract other compounds from different parts of the plant. Different antimicrobial techniques, aside from the Kirby-Bauer method, focus on anti-inflammatory, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, and anti-tumor properties.

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REFERENCES

- Ancheeva, E., Daletos, G., & Proksch, P. (2020). Endophytes from medicinal plants: Promising source of bioactive metabolites. *Journal of Natural Products*, 83(3), 676–683. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.9b01123>
- Agrawal, S., Chen, T., & Yadav, S. (2023). Recent advances in plant-based secondary metabolites. *Bioactive Compounds*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bicomp.2023.112349>
- Cannas, R., Sitzia, M., Fiori, M., Floris, I., Piras, P., & Melis, P. M. (2015). Exploring the cytotoxicity and potential uses of medicinal plant extracts. *Natural Product Research*, 29(12), 1163–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2014.1002835>
- Chua, M. T., & Nicholas, M. (2023). Phytochemicals in Southeast Asia: Functional foods and health benefits. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 302, 115675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2022.115675>
- Firbas, P., & Amon, T. (2014). Chromosome damage studies in the onion plant *Allium cepa* L. *Caryologia*, 67(1), 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00087114.2014.891696>.
- Gao, Y., Liu, X., & Feng, L. (2018). Endophytic fungi from medicinal plants as potential antimicrobial agents. *Microbiological Research*, 207, 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2017.10.003>
- Hudzicki, J., 2009 (Author). American Society for Microbiology, 2016 (Publisher). Kirby- Bauer Disk Diffusion Susceptibility Test Protocol. Retrieved from [https://asm.org/getattachment/2594ce26-bd44-47f6-8287-0657aa9185ad/Kirby- Bauer-Disk-Diffusion-Susceptibility-Test-Protocol-pdf](https://asm.org/getattachment/2594ce26-bd44-47f6-8287-0657aa9185ad/Kirby-Bauer-Disk-Diffusion-Susceptibility-Test-Protocol-pdf).
- Ingente, M. A. G., & Anselmo, C. T. (2024). Phytoremediation potential of Kangkong (*Ipomoea reptans* Poir) in lead-induced hydroponic system. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 11(7). <https://doi.org/10.51244/IJRSI.2024.1107072>
- Jaradat, N. A., Abualhasan, M., & Rahal, H. (2024). Antibacterial activities of traditional medicinal plants used in the Middle East. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 62, 45–54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13880209.2023.2030123>
- Kumar, D. A. S., & Parasurama, D. S. (2024). Plant Bioactive Compounds: Crucial Pharmacological Properties and Role of Elicitors in Enhancing Production. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 58(4), 1034–1053. <https://doi.org/10.5530/ijper.58.4.115>

- Masi, M., Maddau, L., Linaldeddu, B. T., Scanu, B., Evidente, A., & Cimmino, A. (2018). Bioactive Metabolites from Pathogenic and Endophytic Fungi of Forest Trees. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 25(2), 208–252. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867324666170314145159>
- Rahman, Wahidur & HOSSAIN, Md & Ali, Md & Sultana, Tania & Hossain, Khandoker. (2021). Detection of extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) producing *Escherichia coli* in chickens. *Turkish Journal of Veterinary Research*. 5. 10.47748/tjvr.893959.
- Raina, R., Verma, P. K., Sharma, A., Gupta, A., Thakur, V., Dogra, N., Agnihotri, R. K., Sharma, R., & Kumar, D. (2023). *Diplazium esculentum* (Retz.) Sw.: A comprehensive review of its ethnopharmacology, phytochemistry, and pharmacological activities. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 305, 116140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2022.116140>
- Riaz, M., Zia-Ul-Haq, M., & Saeed, M. (2016). Plant-based products: Trends and benefits in the health industry. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 10(8), 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JMPR2015.5962>
- Roy, S., Hazra, B., Mandal, N., & Chaudhuri, T. K. (2013). Assessment of the Antioxidant and Free Radical Scavenging Activities of Methanolic Extract of *Diplazium esculentum*. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 16(6), 1351–1370. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10942912.2011.587382>
- Roy, S., & Chaudhuri, T. K. (2020). A comprehensive review on the pharmacological properties of *Diplazium esculentum*, an edible fern. *Journal of Pharmaceutics and Pharmacology Research*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.31579/2693-7247/014>
- Sarah, QS., Anny, FC., & Misbahuddin, M. (2017). Brine shrimp lethality assay. *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology*, 12:186-189
- Semwal, P. et. al., (2021). *Diplazum esculentum* (Retz.) Sw.: Ethnomedicinal, Phytochemical, and Pharmacological Overview of the Himalayan Ferns. Accessed from <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/1917890>
- Surya, Sunelsya & Pringgenies, Delianis & Ari Setyati, Willis & Syaifudien Bahry, Muhammad. (2022). Investigation of leaves of *Xylocarpus granatum* as a larvicide agent against *Aedes aegypti* and its associated antibacterial properties. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 15. 635-640. 10.30574/wjarr.2022.15.1.0709.
- Zannah, F., Amin, M., Suwono, H., & Lukiati, B. (2017). Phytochemical screening of *Diplazium esculentum* as a medicinal plant from Central Kalimantan, Indonesia. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 1844, 050001. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4983439>